

FILED
2025 MAY 30 A 10:30
UNITED STATES DISTRICT COURT

FOR THE EASTERN DISTRICT OF VIRGINIA

Alexandria Division

Kazim Ali,

Plaintiff,

v.

Commonwealth of Virginia, et al.,

Defendants.

Civil Action No. 1:25-cv-00859-LMB-WBP

NOTICE OF APPEAL

Notice is hereby given that the Plaintiff, Dr. Kazim Ali, pro se, hereby appeals to the United States Court of Appeals for the Fourth Circuit from the following final orders and judgment entered by the U.S. District Court for the Eastern District of Virginia:

1. The Order entered on May 27, 2025 (Dkt. No. 7), dismissing Plaintiff's Complaint [Dkt. No. 1] without prejudice and denying Plaintiff's Motion to Proceed In Forma Pauperis [Dkt. No. 2], Motion for Temporary Restraining Order [Dkt. No. 3], and Motion for Preliminary Injunction [Dkt. No. 4] as moot.
2. The Judgment entered on May 27, 2025 (Dkt. No. 8), which entered judgment in favor of the Defendants pursuant to Federal Rule of Civil Procedure 55, despite no default or hearing, and contrary to the dismissal "without prejudice."

Plaintiff asserts that these actions collectively deprived him of due process and improperly foreclosed constitutional claims without adjudication on the merits.

Dated: May 30, 2025

Respectfully submitted,

Dr. Kazim Ali

Pro Se Plaintiff

6650 High Valley On

Alexandria, VA 22315

UNITED STATES DISTRICT COURT

FOR THE EASTERN DISTRICT OF VIRGINIA

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Kazim Ali,

Plaintiff,

v.

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Defendants.

Civil Action No. 1:25-cv-00859-LMB-WBP

MOTION TO PROCEED IN FORMA PAUPERIS ON APPEAL

Pursuant to Rule 24(a)(1) of the Federal Rules of Appellate Procedure, the Plaintiff, Dr. Kazim Ali, respectfully moves this Court for leave to proceed in forma pauperis on appeal in the above-captioned matter.

Plaintiff is unable to pay the \$505 filing fee due to financial hardship, having experienced prolonged homelessness and legal retaliation. Plaintiff believes the appeal presents substantial constitutional questions and is not taken for delay or frivolous purposes.

An affidavit in support of this motion is attached.

Dated: May 30 , 2025

Respectfully submitted,

Dr. Kazim Ali

Pro Se Plaintiff

6650 High Valley On

Alexandria, VA 22315

Signature: _____

A handwritten signature in black ink, consisting of several overlapping loops and a long horizontal stroke at the bottom, written over a horizontal line.

**AFFIDAVIT IN SUPPORT OF MOTION TO PROCEED IN FORMA
PAUPERIS**

I, Dr. Kazim Ali, declare under penalty of perjury that:

1. I am the Plaintiff in this appeal.
2. I am unable to pay the costs of this appeal due to financial hardship. I have no significant assets, savings, or income, and have faced periods of homelessness since 2023.
3. I respectfully request to proceed without prepayment of fees and believe this appeal is made in good faith and raises constitutional issues involving due process and equal protection.

Executed on this 30th of May, 2025.

Signature: _____

Name: Dr. Kazim Ali

**IN THE UNITED STATES DISTRICT COURT
FOR THE EASTERN DISTRICT OF VIRGINIA**

Alexandria Division

Kazim Ali)	
)	
Plaintiff,)	
v.)	Civil Action No. 1:25-cv-00859-LMB-WBP
)	
Commonwealth of Virginia et al)	
)	
Defendant.)	

JUDGMENT

Pursuant to the order of this Court entered on May 27, 2025 and in accordance with Federal Rules of Civil Procedure 55, JUDGMENT is hereby entered in favor of the Defendant's Commonwealth of Virginia, Randy Bellows, Steve Descano, Penny Azcarate, Kristi Smith, Kevin Davis, Jason S. Miyares, Carrie Poulin, Carl R. Schoenherr, Matthew E. Hughes and against the Plaintiff Kazim Ali.

FERNANDO GALINDO, CLERK OF COURT

By: _____ /s/ _____
S. Brown, Deputy Clerk

Dated: 5/27/2025
Alexandria, Virginia

The following transaction was entered on 5/27/2025 at 4:36 PM EDT and filed on 5/27/2025

Case Name: Ali v. Commonwealth of Virginia et al

Case Number: [1:25-cv-00859-LMB-WBP](#)

Filer:

Document Number: [8](#)

Docket Text:

JUDGMENT is hereby entered in favor of the Defendant's Commonwealth of Virginia, Randy Bellows, Steve Descano, Penny Azcarate, Kristi Smith, Kevin Davis, Jason S. Miyares, Carrie Poulin, Carl R. Schoenherr, Matthew E. Hughes and against the Plaintiff Kazim Ali Pursuant to the order of this Court entered on May 27, 2025 and in accordance with Federal Rules of Civil Procedure 55. Signed by Clerk on 5/27/2025. (Sbro,)

1:25-cv-00859-LMB-WBP Notice has been

The following transaction was entered on 5/27/2025 at 4:11 PM EDT and filed on 5/27/2025

Case Name: Ali v. Commonwealth of Virginia et al
Case Number: [1:25-cv-00859-LMB-WBP](#)
Filer:
Document Number: [7](#)

Docket Text:
ORDERED that the Complaint [Dkt. No. 1] is **DISMISSED WITHOUT PREJUDICE**; and it is hereby **ORDERED** that the Motions to Proceed in forma pauperis [Dkt. No. 2], for Temporary Restraining Order [Dkt. No. 3] and Preliminary Injunction [Dkt. No. 4] be and are **DENIED** as moot (See Order for further details). Signed by District Judge Leonie M. Brinkema on 5/27/2025. (Sbro,)

1:25-cv-00859-LMB-WBP Notice has been electronically mailed to:

